

APPLICATION OF LISTENING METHODOLOGY IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *In this article, the application of the listening method, the useful aspects of teaching foreign languages by listening are briefly discussed. The article mainly talks about the psychology of listening and how important listening is for a person.*

Key words: *listening, foreign languages, method, empathy, listening levels, reflective, listening levels.*

Listening is a receptive type of speech activity, with the help of which the process of receiving and further processing speech messages is carried out based on the operation of the auditory analyzer. Like speech, listening refers to the types of speech activities that carry out oral communication in any situation and in the field of communication. Therefore, communication is effective only if absolute mutual understanding is achieved. The purpose of listening is carried out on the topic of activity and consists in identifying semantic relations, understanding the speech message received by the ear produced by the speaker, understanding and restoring this idea. When listening, the subject, content of someone's thoughts is revealed based on probability forecast, analysis of the semantic relations of the statement and their further synthesis. A meaningful decision is called a listening unit.

Listening mechanisms are general functional mechanisms of memory, advanced reflection mechanisms, etc.

A listening product is a conclusion based on the results of a person's listening process and internal understanding of another person's thoughts, selection, identification of semantic connections, intra-concept correspondence.

Comprehension is the process of discovering and creating semantic relationships between defined concepts, words. The result of understanding can be positive (correct understanding) or negative (incorrect understanding). Listening, understanding, comprehension, multifaceted human psychology does not fail to have its influence. A person imagines what he listens to through his brain, thinks, and strives to reach the end. This is one of the human characteristics.

There are several ways to teach listening in the methodology of teaching foreign languages: as a means of teaching other types of speech activity and as an educational goal. According to Galskova N.D., listening can be used as a tool. They are:

- method of organizing the educational process;
- method of oral introduction of language material;
- tools for teaching other types of speech activity;
- means of monitoring and strengthening acquired knowledge, skills and competences.

Based on the works of Galskova N.D. Gez N.D. considered the following: "Careful organization of the educational process (clarity and consistency of presentation, maximum reliance on language experience, diverse methods of presentation) allows students to focus on moments that will help them program their future." In training with perceptual material, the author concludes that it is necessary to present a specific situation before students listen to the text, depending on which perception is passive or active, which contributes to the successful operation of memory.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-6

Listening is a receptive activity, and mastering receptive activities is the main condition for the development of production skills and, first of all, speech. Therefore, the conclusion about the need for special, targeted training in listening as an independent type of speech activity is clear. The problem of teaching to understand the original speech by ear is one of the most important aspects of teaching communication in a foreign language, therefore, it is extremely important to develop and develop listening teaching technologies that meet the requirements of the time.

Experimental technology

One of the requirements of the program for the level of preparation of the English language of elementary school students is the ability to hear the speech of the teacher, classmates, the content of small texts containing the studied vocabulary based on visual clarity. And the teacher sets himself the task of finding such methods and methods that ensure the success of the child in teaching listening. The teacher should not be limited in his work on the independent processing of materials for the lesson through educational and methodological complexes. Having mastered the methodological goal of the manual, the teacher tries to use various non-standard listening tasks, in which students develop language skills, master the language as a means of communication.

Listening is a very difficult type of speech activity, so when choosing material, the teacher should consider the following points:

- age of students;
- vocabulary;
- level of language proficiency;
- student interests;
- natural speech;
- sound recording quality.

Methodists Filatov V.M., Galskova N.D. divided listening exercises into preparatory and speech processes. The system of educational and preparatory exercises should be aimed at the perception and recognition of sounds, sound combinations, words, phrases, intonation, and the grammatical form of the word. Speaking exercises help to develop comprehension skills.

In conclusion, it can be said that the level of remembering the information heard through one's ears is higher than that of remembering what one sees through one's eyes. Therefore, the knowledge you are teaching and learning is more effective if you learn it by listening. We face many difficulties in learning a foreign language. For example, learning and pronouncing new words and being able to use them in everyday life is one of the important issues. Instead of reading a new foreign word ten, twenty, thirty times, if the learner repeats the word out loud five times, or it is enough to listen to movies, cartoons, songs with that word. The more you listen, the easier it is to learn and the more fluent your words will be.

References:

1. Jumayeva, M. (2021). ORGANIZATION OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. Янгиланаётган Ўзбекистонда фан, таълим ва инновация уйғунлиги мавзусидаги республика 9–сон кўп тармоқли илмий-масофавий онлайн конференцияси 1-қисм.
2. Jumayeva, M. B., & Shukhratovna, M. M. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH GRAMMAR. Science and innovation, 1(Special Issue 2), 608-611.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-6

3. Jumayeva, M. B., & Yakubovich, Y. O. (2023). TEACHING ENGLISH WRITING SKILLS TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(2), 211-215.
4. Jumayeva, M. B., & Yusupov, O. Y. (2023). USING DIFFERENT GAMES AND SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(4), 107-111.
5. Jumayeva, M., & Mamajonova, N. (2022). MODERN METHODS IN EDUCATION: ONLINE LANGUAGE LEARNING. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1035-1038.
6. Jumayeva, M., & Rashidova, M. (2022). THE ROLE OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1448-1452.
7. Jumayeva, M., Isheryakova, J., & Mahmudova, M. (2022). FAIRY TALES AS A PHENOMENON THAT PLAYS AN ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTELLECT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1080-1082.
8. Lurie A.S. Tinglashni o'rgatish usullari. - M., -1988. - 32 s.
9. Mirolyubov, A. A. Chet tillarini o'qitishning umumiy usullari.
10. Mukarrama, J., Jasurbek, A., & Kamoliddin, S. (2022). Teaching listening skills in English.

